

CURRENT ISSUES IN INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY PROTECTION (COPYRIGHT AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNOLOGIES)

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ABSTRACT

This paper explores the specific features of intellectual property, as well as methods of protecting it in the era of artificial intelligence development, and offers recommendations for the development of legal regulation of artificial intelligence. To fully explore the topic, it is necessary to understand the nature of artificial intelligence and copyright, identify the main challenges encountered in this field, assess the impact of artificial intelligence on copyright, and develop recommendations for improving legislation in this area. The study employs a systematic approach, a generalisation method and a predictive research method; the use of these methods enables the key aspects of the topic to be explored and well-founded conclusions to be drawn. The study identified issues related to legislation governing intellectual property matters. It was determined that current legislation is still evolving and does not fully regulate authorship issues as a whole. The analysis revealed the need to develop specific regulations governing these matters in our country..

The relevance of the topic stems from the rapid development of artificial intelligence, which, in turn, is applied in most activities and has the ability to create various works and similar objects protected by copyright. All these processes give rise to new questions regarding the determination of authorship and the protection of this right, as the work is created by artificial intelligence and the identity of the author remains in question. It is precisely in this way that artificial intelligence technology influences the field of copyright. It should be noted that measures are already being taken in our country to develop intellectual property; for example, Article 53 of the new version of the Constitution states that: Everyone is guaranteed freedom of scientific, technical and artistic creativity, and the right to enjoy cultural achievements. Intellectual property is protected by law.

The State shall ensure the cultural, scientific and technical development of society¹.

¹. Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. (2023). Adopted by a national referendum on 30 April 2023. Tashkent: Republic of Uzbekistan <https://lex.uz/docs/6445147>

Furthermore, the significance of the topic is linked to its impact at the international level. The Convention establishing the World Intellectual Property Organisation contains provisions on the protection of intellectual property worldwide, as enshrined in Article 2 of the document: The Organisation has the following objectives:

(i) to promote the protection of intellectual property throughout the world through cooperation amongst States and, where appropriate, in conjunction with any other international organisation;

(ii) to ensure administrative cooperation between the Unions².

It is necessary to analyse the views of other researchers on this topic in order to achieve a high-quality result. Gallyamova A.A. raised the question of who is the rights holder of a work created by AI, since AI is not a legal entity³. From the perspective of this paper, the conclusion is that the author of a work created by Artificial Intelligence is the person who programmed the AI that produced the work, since AI lacks consciousness and the desire to create art. In the author's view, AI cannot be the subject of legal rights. This paper presents entirely logical examples and arguments, and it contributes to the consideration of the aforementioned factors in other studies when amendments are made to legislation.

As a result of the research, it can be said that the objectives set have been achieved and that this topic requires further study. This is because introducing new concepts that are still in the process of development is a complex procedure. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, there are legislative acts regulating the field of intellectual property; however, as noted, the issue of authorship of works created by AI is still under consideration. For example, the country has adopted the law 'On Amendments and Additions to Certain Legislative Acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan in Connection with the Regulation of Relations Arising from the Application of Artificial Intelligence'⁴. As regards recommendations, it should be noted that it is necessary to determine the legal status of works created by AI and to strengthen international cooperation in the field of intellectual property protection..

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². Convention Establishing the World Intellectual Property Organisation. Signed on 14 July 1967. Stockholm. Entered into force in 1970

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³ Gallyamova, A. A. (2023). Copyright in works created using artificial intelligence technologies. *Education and Law*, (4), 240–248.

⁴ Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan 'On Amendments and Additions to Certain Legislative Acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan in Connection with the Regulation of Relations Arising from the Application of Artificial Intelligence'. Adopted on 12 August 2025. Approved on 1 November 2025. <https://lex.uz/docs/7865594>

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